

Synthesis of Heterocycles from 4-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-1-phenylpyrazole

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4-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-1-phenylpyrazole (1) has been used in the synthesis of benzofuran (2), coumarin (5) and benzisoxazole (9).

In continuation with our studies on biologically active heterocycles¹, we describe herein the synthesis of some heterocycles derived from 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-1-phenylpyrazole (1).

The synthesis of compound 1 from 3-formylchromone has been reported^{2,3}. Compound 1 on reaction with ω -bromoacetophenone in acetone/potassium carbonate yielded benzofuran (2). The coumarin (5) was synthesised via the α , β -unsaturated ester (4) which was obtained by dehydration of the β -hydroxyester (3). The ester (3) was prepared from 1 and ethyl bromoacetate by the Reformatsky reaction. Attempts to prepare the coumarin (5) via the acetate (6) were unsuccessful.

Compound 1 on treatment with hydroxylamine under neutral or mildly alkaline aqueous conditions yielded an oxime (7). Treatment of 7 with HCl provided a mixture of a benzisoxazole (9) and an amide (10) by cyclodehydration and Beckmann rearrangement respectively. Compound 9 could alternatively be prepared by gently heating the oxime

acetate (8) under vacuum. The amide was identified by alkaline degradation to 2-aminophenol (11) and 1-phenylpyrazole-4-carboxylic acid (12).

Compounds 1-12 were evaluated in vitro for their antimicrobial activity at 1 mg ml⁻¹ in a nutrient agar medium by the Ditch-plate method⁴ against *S. aureus* FDA209P, and several other clinically resistant *S. aureus* strains, *Proteus vulgaris*, *S. faecalis*, *Pseudomonas*, *Aspergillus* and *Candida*. Compound 6 showed significant activity against both *Aspergillus* and *Candida*, and compound 8 had moderate activity against *S. aureus* FDA209P.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian spectrophotometer (60 MHz) downfield from TMS as internal standard. Satisfactory elemental analysis was obtained for all the compounds.

2-Benzoyl-3-(1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)benzofuran (2): A mixture of compound 1 (0.529 g, 0.002 mol), ω -bromoacetophenone (0.422 g, 0.002 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (~2 g) was refluxed for 6 h in dry acetone (20 ml) under anhydrous conditions. The solvent was then vacuum-distilled, the residue washed with ice-water and the resulting solid crystallised from ethanol, (0.714 g, 98%), m.p. 133°; δ (CDCl₃) 7.2-8.0 (14H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, pyrazole H-5) and 8.8 (1H, s, pyrazole H-3); ν_{\max} 1 660 (benzoyl C=O), 1 600, 1 575 and 1 540 cm⁻¹.

Ethyl 3-hydroxy-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)propanoate (3): A mixture of anhydrous zinc powder (0.196 g, 0.003 mol) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.3 ml, ~0.0025 mol) was refluxed in dry benzene (15 ml) for 30 min. A solution of 1 (0.529 g, 0.002 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml) was then added and the mixture refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was washed with cold dilute H₂SO₄ (10%; 200 ml) and extracted with benzene. The organic extract was washed with water and vacuum-distilled to give a low melting yellow product.

Ethyl 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)-2-propenoate (4): To a solution of **3** in dry benzene (20 ml), pyridine (0.3 ml) and thionyl chloride (0.25 ml) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then treated with ice-cold water and the benzene layer washed with cold dilute HCl (10%) followed by cold NaHCO₃ (5%) and water. The solvent was concentrated to yield a light brown solid which was dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148°.

4-(1-Phenylpyrazole-4-yl)coumarin (5): The ester **4** was dissolved in a minimum amount of concentrated H₂SO₄ and allowed to stand for 12 h at room temperature. The mixture was then poured into ice-water, the solution extracted with chloroform and the chloroform layer washed with cold dilute NaOH (5%) followed by water. Silica gel (0.2 g) was added to the chloroform solution and the mixture was stirred and filtered. The residue obtained by vacuum-distillation of the filtrate was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to yield a pale yellow amorphous powder, m.p. 162°; δ (CDCl₃) 6.8 (1H, s, coumarin H-3), 7.1–7.8 (m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, H-5 of pyrazole) and 8.5 (1H, s, H-3 of pyrazole); ν_{\max} 1 665 (coumarin C=O), 1 620, 1 595 and 1 540 cm⁻¹.

4-(2-Acetoxybenzoyl)-1-phenylpyrazole (6): A mixture of **1** (0.264 g, 0.001 mol) and fused sodium acetate (~0.2 g) was refluxed in acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was crystallised from 50% aqueous ethanol, (0.251 g, 82%), m.p. 113° (lit.³ 113°).

4-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-1-phenylpyrazole oxime (7). *Method 1*: A mixture of **1** (0.264 g, 0.001 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.083 g, 0.0012 mol) in aqueous KOH (2 ml; 40%) was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. The solid obtained on acidification with dilute HCl (25%) was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (0.251 g, 90%), m.p. 202°. *Method 2*: A mixture of **1** (0.264 g, 0.001 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.083 g, 0.0012 mol) and sodium acetate (1 g) were heated at 60–70° in ethanol (10 ml) for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-water and filtered. The residue was dissolved in cold dilute NaOH (10%), filtered, reprecipitated with cold dilute HCl (10%) and crystallised from ethanol, (0.243 g, 87%), m.p. 202°; ν_{\max} 3 400–2 800 (bonded OH), 1 630–1 600, 1 580, 1 550 and 1 500 cm⁻¹.

The oxime prepared by both the methods was identical (tlc and m.m.p.).

2-(1-Phenylpyrazol-4-yl)benzoxazole (9) and 2-(1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)amidophenol (10) from oxime (7): The oxime **7** (0.279 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed

in acetic acid-HCl (1 : 1; 5 ml) for 3 h and the reaction mixture then poured onto ice. The resulting solid was washed with water, stirred in cold aqueous KOH (10%; 10 ml) for 15 min and filtered. The residue was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give the benzoxazole (**9**; 0.105 g, 40%), m.p. 150°; δ (CDCl₃) 7.2–7.8 (9H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, pyrazole H-5), 8.65 (1H, s, pyrazole H-3); ν_{\max} 1 645 (benzoxazole C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹. The filtrate was neutralised with cold dilute HCl (10%) and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from 50% aqueous ethanol to give the amide (**10**; 0.140 g, 50%), m.p. 217°; ν_{\max} 3 430 (NH), 3 300–3 000 (ArOH), 1 650 (amide I band), 1 625 and 1 605 cm⁻¹.

Oxime acetate (8): A solution of **7** (0.279 g, 0.001 mol) in acetic anhydride (1 ml) was stirred for 5 min at room temperature, then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid crystallised from ethanol, (0.283 g, 78%), m.p. 90°.

2-(1-Phenylpyrazol-4-yl)-benzoxazole (9) from the oxime acetate (8): The oxime acetate (**8**; 0.363 g, 0.001 mol) was heated at 120° under reduced pressure for 30 min. The solid obtained on cooling was crystallised from ethanol, (0.118 g, 35%), m.p. 150°.

The benzoxazole obtained from the oxime and the oxime acetate was identical (tlc and m.m.p.).

Hydrolysis of 2-(1-phenylpyrazol-4-yl)amidophenol (10): To the amide (**10**; 0.1 g) dissolved in a minimum of ethanol, was added aqueous KOH (5%, 2 ml) and the solution refluxed vigorously for 3 h. Ethanol was then distilled off, the solution acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 4-carboxy-1-phenylpyrazole (**12**), m.p. 220° (lit.³ 221°; lit.⁶ 219–220°). The filtrate was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, extracted with diethyl ether and the ether evaporated to yield 2-aminophenol (**11**), m.p. 170°.

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